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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

The authors have highlighted the role of the export market in Angola and investigated the country's comparative advantage in products other than Oil and Diamonds, which are currently reported to account for over 80% of the nation's GDP. The information provided is aimed at the facilitation of product diversification in Angola's export portfolio which is currently thin. The authors found that Angola has comparative advantage in 351 product lines. The highest comparative advantage (178.8) is for powders/flakes of aluminum of lamellar structure. Diamonds and oil were not among the top 50 products on the basis of revealed comparative advantage. The authors concluded that because Angola has comparative advantage in a wide range of product lines other than oil and diamonds, the country should improve its business operating environment and embark on strategic international marketing to increase earnings from its endowment. They recommended that Angola's export development programme should contribute to equal distribution of wealth and that the government should enact laws and commit itself to stamping out corruption.

Keywords: Revealed comparative advantage, Decision(s) mix, Export promotion, International trade.

INTRODUCTION

A country and its industries at one point have to make marketing decisions in foreign countries which will aid them in selling their products in which they have comparative advantage. A country with comparative advantage will have demonstrated that it has capabilities and specializes in the production of the products in which comparative advantage exists. Products that have been produced at an advantage may be exported and success in the industry can be aided by international marketing. The objective of this paper is to highlight the role of the export market in Angola and investigate whether Angola has comparative advantage in products other than oil and diamonds, commodities which it successfully exports (Le Billon, 2001). Angola is a member of the Southern African Development Community (SADC), hence the authors interest as nationals of this community.

BACKGROUND ON ANGOLA

Angola has experienced very high growth rates in recent years which have been spurred by the export of oil and diamonds. Over the past decade growth has almost been entirely driven by rising oil production which surpassed 1.4 million barrels per day in late 2005 and was expected to grow to 2 million barrels per day by 2007. Reported statistics for economic growth are 18% in 2005, 26% in 2006 and 17.6% in 2007 (Rosenblum, 2011). In the period 2001–2010, Angola had the world's highest annual average GDP growth, at 11.1 percent. However, due to the global recession the economy contracted an estimated –0.3% in 2009 (The Economist, 2008).

Factors which have aided growth in Angola include 1) The end of the 25 year civil war allowing the government to refocus resources towards the economy rather than war or corruption (Rosenblum, 2011), 2) the joining of the Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) in 2006 (Rosenblum, 2011) under which it was allocated a quota of 1.65 million barrels per day, this has aided the country to participate effectively in the global oil market, 3) the negotiation for better terms with international firms whom have invested in the oil sector and mining of diamonds (Collier, 2009). These measures have resulted in high exports and economic growth (UNDP, 2008). In

addition to favourable local conditions, success in the oil industry can also be attributed to the favorable price of its oil on the international market (Rosenblum, 2011).

Oil production and related activities account for over 80% of Angola's GDP. Diamonds additionally account for 5% of the GDP (Index Mundi, 2013). These statistics show Angola's heavy reliance on oil and diamonds. It is imperative for the country to exploit other commodities in which Angola has comparative advantage for the export market. This is important if it is to avoid what is referred to as a resource curse/Dutch disease (Rosenblum, 2011). Countries with Dutch Disease typically display high economic growth rates as a result of high commodity prices. However, they also risk the consequences of sudden or sharp drops in commodity prices. Additionally, the healthy growth rates hide the fact that the economy is not growing smartly, which includes diversifying the industrial base (Brahmbhatt *et al.*, 2010).

Angola needs to assess its export base and invest in products in which it has a comparative advantage. Once identification has been completed, the success of exporting these products will in part depend on strategic international marketing. Dole and Lowe (2008) and Mzumara (2012) have highlighted the planning steps in international marketing. The planning steps involve situational analysis, development of marketing strategies, execution of the marketing plan and the control process. For success in exploiting its product base, Angola can learn from some of the marketing strategies it has employed to boost the performance of the oil industry e.g. (joining global or regional organizations that facilitate the marketing of a commodity as they did in the case of joining OPEC). This paper seeks to use revealed comparative advantage to review Angola's commodity profile and proffer suggestions for diversifying its marketed products. According to Widgrén (2005), the logic of using revealed comparative advantage is to assess comparative advantage of a given country's specialization in exports in relation to some reference group.

Comparative Advantage

In Economics, comparative advantage refers to the ability of a party to produce a particular good or service at a lower marginal and opportunity cost over another (Baumol and Blinder, 2009). A comparative advantage as described in the Heckscher –Ohin theorem is attributed to factor endowment (Widgrén, 2005). That means a country endowed with a particular factor will produce products using that factor that is in abundance. Consequently the countries will import goods which use scarce resources. Case and Fair (2002) also state that a country possesses comparative advantage in producing a particular good if it is sufficiently endowed with inputs used to produce the particular product.

The result of different factor endowments is that specialization will appear as countries concentrate on the products they have an advantage in producing through factor endowment. These are the products the country will export to other nations because they are produced efficiently in that country compared to other nations. In so doing, the world economy and its inhabitants will gain from engaging in international trade (Mzumara, 2006, 2012).

METHODOLOGY

The authors have used Balassa (1965) revealed comparative advantage to measure comparative advantage for selected products in Angola. The technique has been used by Krugell and Matthee (2009) to measure export capabilities of the Southern African internal regions.

The Balassa (1965) formula is in the form of:

$$RCA = \left(\frac{X_{i,j}}{X_{w,j}} \right) / \left(\frac{X_{i,tot}}{X_{w,tot}} \right)$$

With:

$X_{i,j}$ denoting country i 's exports of product j ;

$X_{i,tot}$ denoting country i 's total exports;

$X_{w,j}$ denoting the world's (all countries) export of product j ; and

$X_{w,tot}$ denoting total exports in the world.

A revealed comparative advantage of equal to and greater than 1 demonstrates that the country has Revealed Comparative Advantage. In other words, the country is specialised in producing and exporting the product line under

consideration. A revealed comparative advantage of less than 1 demonstrates that the country is not specialised in the product line.

Global export data and Angola's export data was obtained from the International Trade Centre's (ITC) Trade Map based in Geneva, Switzerland. Data was collected for the period 2008 - 2010. Then a revealed comparative advantage was computed for each product code for 2008, 2009 and 2010. An average revealed comparative advantage for every product code was obtained using data from the three years. The data used the harmonized 6-digit level classification; the best disaggregated and internationally recognized classification of products.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results illustrated that Angola has 351 products lines with a revealed comparative advantage index equal to or greater than 1. This demonstrated that Angola is specialised in the production of these 351 product lines compared to the rest of the world. Table 1 shows 50 top products out of the 351.

Table 1: 50 top products with the highest revealed comparative advantage (RCA) in Angola

Product code	Product description	RCA2008	RCA2009	RCA 2010	RCA
760320	Powders/flakes, aluminum, of lamellar structure	129.1099	241.3813	165.8641	178.7851
380700	Wood tar, tar oil creosote naphtha	54.41604	226.1907	201.7655	160.7907
570190	Carpets of materials, knotted	154.4577	190.5369	136.7276	160.5741
520548	Combed yarn mult cotton	111.3896	224.0798	125.7195	153.7297
581100	Quilted textile products in the piece (not embroidered)	141.743	144.2763	155.6061	147.2085
690710	Unglazed ceramic flags, tiles wider than 7cm	103.32	165.5728	112.7904	127.2277
690810	Glazed ceramic mosaic tiles, cubes & similar < 7cm wide	90.54633	109.7544	111.4965	103.9324
701391	Glassware except kitchen, tableware of lead crystal	96.88676	115.378	88.49935	100.2547
700320	Cast glass sheet, wired	59.8529	115.0878	82.69793	85.87955
281420	Ammonia in aqueous solution	38.1639	76.95905	104.309	73.14397
293354	Derivatives of malonylurea (barbituric acid)(excluding of 2933.53); salts	48.98288	69.59266	94.85766	71.1444
530110	Flax fibre, raw or retted	13.46803	100.2341	97.30028	70.33414
550820	Sewing thread of artificial staple fibre	62.59593	81.69428	61.83857	68.70959
540500	Artificial monofilament >67 dtex <1mm, strip, straw t<5mm	42.14381	81.25133	73.00294	65.46603
740911	Plate, sheet strip, refined copper, coil, t>0.15mm	40.23463	84.86314	50.60151	58.44412
700330	Cast glass profiles	34.09035	83.55518	55.38932	57.67828
540332	Yarn, viscose rayon, single >120 turn/m, not retail	48.45865	72.69175	50.60151	57.25064
230690	Vegetable oil-cake and other solid residue	41.17175	77.917788	41.01254	53.36739
630291	Toilet or kitchen linen of cotton	36.06022	59.04798	44.50012	46.53611

630299	Toilet or kitchen linen, of material	38.44314	56.35261	44.29694	46.36423
721310	Hot rolled bar/rod grooved iron or non-alloy steel	26.28232	63.2355	44.98067	44.83283
520544	Cotton yarn >85% multiple combed 192-125 dtex, not retail	30.1733	46.24961	45.06436	40.49576
620349	Men's, boys trousers & shorts, material, not knit	29.28116	41.51819	50.27079	40.35671
381700	Mixed alkylbenzenes & mixed alkylnaphthalenes	29.70048	49.75997	39.11116	39.52387
410419	Tanned/crust hides & skins of bovine (including buffalo)/equine animals	27.13507	47.22567	35.02711	36.46262
251512	Marble and travertine in blocks	30.50271	35.87583	38.10943	34.82933
720826	Flat rld prod/coils > 4.75	20.29372	48.37826	27.55068	32.07422
271290	Mineral waxes	14.37806	42.87357	29.14369	28.79844
271210	Petroleum jelly	26.68752	36.16589	23.016	28.62314
520710	Cotton yarn (except sewing thread) >85% cotton, retail	23.52989	34.01688	27.07211	28.20629
291250	Cyclic polymers of aldehydes	16.72202	32.578	31.18655	26.8886
310210	Urea, including aqueous solution in pads>10kg	19.26006	34.5629	26.65606	26.82634
620791	Men's, boys dressing gowns, etc. cotton, not knit	19.44106	31.86529	26.87433	26.06023
392210	Baths, shower-baths and wash basins of plastic	17.39179	29.16398	24.40683	23.41225
750890	Articles of nickel	18.71631	27.7465	23.77394	23.41225
630319	Curtains drapes blinds valances, synthetic fibre	15.89315	27.20917	26.61457	23.23896
530129	Flax fibre, otherwise processed but not spun	20.97452	28.90918	19.2758	23.05317
280300	Carbon (carbon blacks and other forms of carbon)	16.34205	30.15258	19.08157	21.85874
720840	Flat rid/prod not in coil	11.96123	31.0376	21.87862	21.16778
520645	Cotton yarn <85% multiple combed <123 dtex	16.09833	25.12724	22.277779	21.16778
252321	Portland cement, white or white artificially coloured	16.32113	24.81808	20.64258	20.59393
540831	Woven fabric of artificial filament unbleached/bleached	13.46821	26.77223	20.88552	20.37532

680221	Cut or swan slabs of marble, travertine or alabaster	16.17512	22.92728	21.74656	20.28299
720390	Spongy iron lumps, pellets etc. >99.94% pure	24.32316	21.47455	11.11776	18.97183
330119	Essential oils of citrus fruits	15.93202	24.31878	16.52089	18.9239
230320	Beet-pulp, bagasse & other waste of sugar manufacture	13.73106	22.07339	20.38546	18.72997
540821	Woven fabric >85% artificial filament/strip unbleached/bleached	13.36012	25.42803	16.57671	18.85495
251511	Marble and crude travertine or roughly trimmed	16.26106	23.09662	14.29358	17.88375
630800	Set, woven fabric and yarn for rugs, tapestry	13.33614	21.66244	18.36019	17.7625
200791	Citrus based jams jellies marmalade etc.	15.1306	20.10977	17.14538	17.46192

Source: Computed using data from Trade Map (2013)

Aluminum powder/flakes of lamellar structure had the highest revealed comparative advantage in Angola, with an index of 178.9 followed by wood tar, tar oil creosote naphtha with an index of 160.8. The third position was occupied by carpets of materials knotted, with an index of 160.6. The fourth position was occupied by combed yarn cotton with an index of 153.7 and the fifth product line was quilted textile with an index of 147.2. The products in which Angola has comparative advantage in consists of manufactured products and as well as primary products. The number of products in which Angola has comparative advantage is very much consistent with an average developing country. The results also demonstrated that Angola conforms to Ricardo's principle of comparative advantage as extended by Hescheker-Ohlin. The results are surprising in that the top 50 products in which Angola is highly specialized do not include oil and diamonds which are currently Angola's most important export products that account for over 85% of the GDP. Angola needs to sustain an appropriate economic diversification programme, through making use of its wide product base in which it has revealed comparative advantage. If this is not done, the event of a drastic shock in the global oil market would destabilise the economy with negative consequences at a national level (Corkin, 2009). This would be similar to that which occurred in Côte D'Ivoire after a decline in the international coffee and cocoa prices. The two commodities accounted for over 80% of the countries revenues before Côte D'Ivoire's economic crisis which was experienced in the 1980s (Demery, 1996).

It is commendable that Angola has in its National Development Plan committed to allocating 5% of its oil revenues towards economic diversification (Corkin, 2009). In addition to this the government has received international support from the Governments of China, Spain, Canada, Brazil and the World Bank to support economic diversification (Corkin, 2009). While this is a step in the right direction recent literature documents some weaknesses in the current diversification policy. A recent report illustrates that oil accounts for 98% of Angola's exports (Jover et al., 2012). This shows that the economic diversification programme has not had much impact on Angola's export portfolio. The Government of Angola could improve this situation by the establishment of an export development policy under the economic diversification programme. Under the policy a percentage of revenues from the oil sector could be allocated to the stimulation of growth in the country's export portfolio. To encourage growth in the export market, the government would in its programmes need to prioritise some of the following issues which have been noted to hamper business in the country. For instance the current operating environment in Angola is challenging and the country ranks 172 out of 183 economies, in the World Bank Doing Business Index, which measures the ease of operating in the private sector (Jover et al, 2012). Angola's business environment scores poorly on the following: dealing with construction permits, getting access to electricity, registering property, access to credit, paying taxes, contract enforcement, resolving companies' insolvency and trading across borders.

(Brenthurst Foundation) 2012 also reports that the current economic diversification programme has been noted to be slow and hampered by long-term electricity blackouts which are a regular feature; this in part has been

attributed to poor planning. An estimated two thirds of the businesses have been reported to rely on their own electricity supply, which drives the cost of local manufacturing up (Jover et al., 2012). In its development planning the government of Angola should among other issues prioritise the creation of a conducive business environment. The development of electricity supply systems should also be prioritised since all other industrial development projects depend on its reliable availability. In addition to the issues discussed earlier in this section corruption is another factor which curtails business development. In its 2011 index, the global corruption watchdog, Transparency International ranked Angola among the 16 most corrupt countries (168 out of 178 countries) (Freedom House, 2011) therefore the government must focus on stamping it out.

Another issue that needs to be addressed in Angola's economic diversification programme is the equitable distribution of wealth. The policies under the export development programme should be pro-poor. Jover et al. (2012) and Corkin (2009) report that despite having an enormous amount of mineral riches, over 50% of Angola's population live under the \$2-per-day poverty line, with one-third reliant on subsistence agriculture for their income. An estimated four decades ago Angola was the world's fourth largest producer of coffee and sisal (Brenthurst Foundation, 2012). In 1974 the coffee exports were valued at \$USD180million, the figure was just \$USD 250000 in 2010 (Brenthurst Foundations, 2012). Angola should work at reviving its agricultural exports. In order for the current economic diversification programme to be equitable and sustainable the government should among other steps include small-holder farmers in its export development programmes. The review of Angola's export portfolio has revealed that the country has a revealed comparative advantage in the following agricultural commodities/products derived from them (cotton; bovine hides; citrus; vegetable oil; sugar cane and sugar beet). These products provide a base on which the country can diversify its export portfolio.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It was concluded that Angola has comparative advantage in a wide range of products other than oil and diamonds. With support to the development of a conducive business environment and a proper international marketing strategy, Angola can definitely improve earnings from its vast endowments and reduce its vulnerability to the Dutch Disease. The author's recommend that Angola should streamline its investment codes into its development plans. Commitment and proper planning is required to enhance energy security in-terms of electricity supply as the industrialization process depends on its availability. The economic policies should also be equitable and pro-poor. Agricultural development should be a key sector for investment as the majority of the population relies on the industry as a source of livelihood. Supportive policies should include those that fight corruption should be put in place, so that the country can benefit from a diversified industry.

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